

Identification of 4Q389 frag. C (PAM 43.688 frag. 62; IAA Plate 349, frag. 18) as yet another 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) fragment

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The series of photographs (PAM 43.660–43.701; publication in DJD 33) of forty plates with more than three thousand small unidentified Qumran Cave 4 fragments was taken in July 1960, at the completion of the Rockefeller-funded work of the international team of editors of the Cave 4 fragments during the 1950s. Later, a few hundred of those fragments were removed by the editors, particularly by John Strugnell, from the plates of unidentified fragments and associated or identified with manuscripts on other plates. The editors of the Cave 4 manuscripts in the 1990s sometimes accepted those identifications, and sometimes did not. In many cases the relocations of these fragments after the 1960 photographs has not been recorded.

The photograph PAM 43.688 (www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285463) contains a fragment, numbered frag. 62 in DJD 33, plate XXVII, which subsequently was removed from that Museum Plate 81, and transferred to Museum Plate 349 which contains the fragments of 4Q389, 4QApocryphon of Jeremiah C^d. New (2013) photographs of the fragment (Plate 349, Frag 18) are accessible on The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, on www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-474760 (full spectrum color) and www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-474761 (infrared).

Screen capture from www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-474761

The editor of 4Q389, Devorah Dimant, recognized that this fragment did not have the same hand as the other 4Q389 fragments, and published it as an unidentified fragment with the reference number 4Q389 frag. C (DJD 30, p. 234).

In my endeavour to identify such unidentified fragments on textual and/or material grounds, and to join them physically to other fragments, I discovered that this fragment can be joined to 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) frags. 10-13 lines 24-25 (see DJD 15, p. 29).

Materially, the fragment joins to 4Q56:

section of 4Q56 (PAM 43.031; screen capture from www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284272) and (indicated with blue arrow) PAM 43.688 frag. 62 (screen capture from www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285463)

Textually, one may now transcribe the two lines with remnants of Isa 19:17-18 as follows (the letters of 4Q389 C in red).

[אליו יפח] ד' מפני תנופת יד יהוה צבאות אש [ר הוא יועץ עליו ביום]	24
[ההוא יהי] ו' חמש ערים בארץ מצרים מדברו [ת שפת כנען ונשבעות]	25

Bibliography:

- DJD 15 Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, X: The Prophets*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 15 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1997)
- DJD 30 Devorah Dimant, *Qumran Cave 4, XXI: Parabiblical Texts, Part 4: Pseudo-Prophetic Texts*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 30 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)
- DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)

For other identifications of 4Q56 fragments see:

Eibert Tigchelaar, "Identification of 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) Fragments," *Revue de Qumran* 31/114 (2019): 275-81

Eibert Tigchelaar, Identification of 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) Fragments, Addition (PAM 43.664 frag. 10). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5123307>